

Global Language Upskilling. Reinforcing the Original Mooc Format

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Abstract. As digital education expanded in the post-pandemic era, Moocs gained traction as a learning tool for the acquisition of specific professional competences. Foreign language was recognized as one of the desirable transversal global skills, potentially contributing to sustainable development at national level, especially English as a lingua franca for international diplomacy and business. This paper sets out to explore whether the original university-led Mooc concept still resonates with a global lifelong learner audience, and whether the self-learning format and pedagogic approach of Moocs constitute a valid and effective tool for professional language development on a global scale. The focus is on the English language Moocs offered by Federica Web Learning, the Centre for Digital Education at the University of Naples Federico II, on the Coursera platform, and their specific “global” design features. The study is based on platform analytics and data from a learner survey.

Keywords: LMoocs, Global upskilling, Workforce empowerment.

1 Language Training via Moocs. Enhancing Global Competence

In today’s rapidly evolving and increasingly interconnected world, it is widely accepted that global competency is required to enable citizens to thrive in such a complex environment. Several frameworks have been designed to define the key knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that global competency involves, (OECD; WHO), and to provide guidance for the institutions who aim to foster their development. These frameworks aim to support SDGs, because one of their main objectives is to enable citizens to engage in effective interaction with people from diverse backgrounds, and to take appropriate and ethical local action in consideration of the global context [1].

Effective communication skills, both linguistic and intercultural, are therefore a cornerstone of global competency [2], and some authors have gone so far as to suggest that foreign language skills are “the ultimate 21st century global competency” [3] as they allow for empowerment in a globalized world [4]. English is still commonly considered

the most important lingua franca [7] [8], and even within the diverse labor market of Europe, knowledge of the English language is a requirement for approximately a quarter of all advertised job vacancies and is one of the most required skills in general¹.

Moocs are deemed to be a permanent feature of the global education and training landscape due to the ever-increasing demand for flexible models of continuing professional development [9]; and Language Moocs (LMoocs) appear to have followed a similar trajectory. Indeed, while Mooc platforms have been criticized for the lack of interaction in the course format and for the cognitive-behavioral pedagogical model used [10], the interest in language Moocs increased massively during the Covid period [11]; together with user demand for high quality, free and accessible language learning resources, to improve skills, oral competence and vocabulary, and opportunities for real-life application [12]. According to some authors, LMoocs are not only one of the most established tools available today as a systematic approach to the need for large-scale language training [13] [14] but they also promote the development of soft skills, including business and learning skills [15] [16]. The challenge that remains is whether it is possible to further improve the design of these courses to enhance interaction, especially with the content, or whether the “convergence” cited by Brown et al. [17] as one of the main trends in online learning today, whereby learners are encouraged to interact with a wide variety of types of learning content, based on different approaches, activating different forms of learning strategies and using different services (internal or external), to create their own learning pathways, discourages learners from following only the predetermined and somewhat prescriptive path of a particular xMooc.

2 The Federica Language Moocs. Enhancing “convergence” to go global

The language course portfolio developed by Federica WebLearning was part of a project aimed at strengthening the workforce of the local public administration sector, in line with the University’s third mission, with a focus on language skills. The strategy was to create a first block of open courses – starting with English B1, as this is a requirement for graduation at bachelor level and a prerequisite for selection procedures in the public sector – in a certified, self-learning mode, in order to build flexible future training packages depending on the different training needs of specific target groups. The courses were characterized by a focus on skills development, task-based learning, learner engagement with the online content and extensive scaffolding in the form of translations and explanations in Italian, the mother tongue of the vast majority of learners at the time. The success of the delivered initiative [18] led to the decision to test the viability of the courses to provide large-scale language training to a global audience of lifelong learners on the international platform Coursera.

Following several studies suggesting the importance of cultural factors in the design of effective and engaging online learning [19] [20], the redesign of the courses was

¹OECD, The demand for language skills in the European labour market: Evidence from online job vacancies, 13 June 2023. Retrieved from: <https://u.garr.it/sEFVy>, last accessed 2025/01/ 20.

driven by the intention to try and create a learning environment in which all learners, whatever their demographic and background, would feel comfortable. One of the first decisions was to teach a global variety of the English language and try to distance it from the specifics of one variety, especially American or British which are often the focus of language learning textbooks. The contextualization of the language comes from animation videos that follow the lives and stories of a set of diverse characters who represent a very broad spectrum of learners in terms of lifestyle and interests and avoid ethnic and gender stereotypes [21]. The second decision was to emphasize a task-based approach in situations which learners might find themselves in and encourage the use of diverse learning tools to accomplish them.

In terms of the actual content of the LMOocs, the courses can be considered comprehensive, as they incorporate elements from each of the 6 modalities identified by the latest LMOoc taxonomies [22]; they offer general language acquisition; include language for academic and professional purposes; develop the four skills and refer to meta-language learning and intercultural competency. There is also an attempt to include “learners’ real-world spaces and their socio-cultural surroundings” [23] and regular submission of automated graded activities is required as it is “a robust indicator towards course success” [24]. In addition, several design principles were adopted to provide scaffolding for a global audience. The number of practice assignments and amount of situational learning was increased; the feedback on the practice assignments was intensified to provide clear but important explanations; gap-fill exercises requiring insertion of words or phrases were eliminated to avoid the demotivating automated correction of minor errors of spelling or punctuation common amongst learners not using Latin alphabet; the dictionaries were improved with extra information (word class, definition, example sentence) and speaking and writing exercises were accompanied by guided feedback for peer review. Visuals, and exercises based on visuals, which require a lot of band width and have poor resolution on Mobile use were also eliminated. For the first time, users also had the opportunity to use the platform’s Ai tutor.

Data analysis was carried out to make an initial assessment of the courses’ ability to create an effective and comfortable learning environment for global users, thanks to the diversification of tools and attention to cultural context.

3 Methodology

Learner data was analyzed in 2 steps. First, platform analytics data provided overall information about the learners, and their reaction to the course content. Secondly, a survey was administered to take a closer look at the perceived relevance and effectiveness of the Federica LMOocs for professional development.

The learner surveys were administered between December 21st 2024 and January 10th 2025 and platform data was downloaded for analysis on December 21st 2024 to coincide. The survey was voluntary, included open as well as multiple choice questions, and also asked learners to indicate their interest in becoming part of a course-related Advanced learning community, for updates on initiatives and opportunities for regular

communication. 774 learners, representing approx. 8% of active learners, responded to the survey and committed to the Learning Community.

4 Widely international and engaged audience

Analysis of the platform data provided an initial snapshot of the overall user-base on the three English language courses on December 21st 2024. The 10,000 active learners (those who completed approx. 30% of the course) are relatively young, 55% female learners, and the majority have some form of university education. Numbers are significantly higher on the Lower intermediate course, and decline as the level increases, possibly indicating the same global need for threshold level competence as identified in Italy.

Most Federica language learners are from Egypt, with Kazakhstan, India, Mexico and Turkey in the top ten. Overall, 20% of Federica learners come from Africa, which is significantly higher than the Coursera average, and 36% are from Asia, and 10% from Latin America. It is interesting to note that 30% of the learners are unemployed and looking for work, so are potentially using the English language courses for upskilling to improve their opportunities in the jobs market. Platform data also show that course fees, for the most part, are paid by organizations (approximately 50%), financial aid or free trial, perhaps indicating that low-cost quality LMOocs still provide valuable support for professional upskilling in various countries around the world. The biggest identified category of organizations is government organizations (at 27%) indicating a widespread need for language upskilling on the part of public administrations in line with recent societal changes, and reinforced by the addition of new governmental organizations to the platform, as from Kazakhstan.

The platform data gives initial indications as to learner satisfaction with the courses. Although all 3 courses were created following exactly the same design, with consistency of number, order and type of learning objects, learner enrolments were much higher on the Lower intermediate B1.1 course, but the completion rate was low, whereas the second part of the same course, B1.2, had fewer learners but a surprising 20% completion rate, and was ranked as one of Coursera's top 50 courses for learner engagement in 2024.

Most students who completed the courses performed well and obtained over 70% final grade on the course. The 20% of learners who completed the course but scored between 50% and 70% in the final grade included a significant percentage of learners from Egypt, Kazakhstan, United Arab Emirates and Morocco, which seems to indicate that the graded assignments on the course pose more difficulties for learners with a non-Latin alphabet, since half of the lower-scoring completers were from countries that use Arabic, Cyrillic or other scripts.

5. Perception of LMOOCs as Resource for Collective Development

In terms of survey data analysis, there were 774 respondents, representing approx. 8% of active users. A committed group, most of whom already completed the course, with 75% of learners spending between 2 and 4 hours on the course each week.

In terms of geographical distribution, the respondents represent 112 different countries. 12 countries had a representation of between 10 and 40 learners, with Mexico, Colombia, Afghanistan, Pakistan and Turkey occupying the top 5 places. However, 100 out of 112 countries had only 1-3 learners from each, so we decided to group our learner countries according to the 7 geographical regions defined by the World Bank², with Latin America and Europe + Central Asia accounting for half of the respondents, and MENA and Sub-Saharan Africa then constituting a further 30%.

Approximately 30% of the respondents in each of the 7 geographical regions chose the audit enrolment option, which may indicate a persistent need for free language tuition, especially since this percentage is much higher than in the overall population of Federica learners on the Coursera platform and since 38 of the countries the learners come from are classified by the World Bank as Low (16) or Lower-middle income (22).

In terms of the relevance of the courses for professional language upskilling, almost a third of the respondents were aged between 41 and 60, which represents a much higher percentage of lifelong learners in this “engaged” learner cohort compared to the overall learner population. 20% of respondents did not have any form of university education which again is higher than the overall population. 59% of the respondents declared themselves in employment, and 20% described themselves as Neets, perhaps reinforcing the idea that these learners were using the courses for professional development or to increase their opportunities in the job market: Very few students were required to follow the course by their employer or university, but did so at their own volition. 20% of respondents explicitly stated that their motivation was to extend their language skills for professional growth and 29% for personal growth. A further 29% of the learners wanted English for academic goals which corresponds to the number of university students enrolled. A fifth of the respondents stated that the LMooCs contributed to their official Continuous Professional Development hours (CPD). It is interesting to note that in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa the LMooCs act as a form of micro-credential, with a tenth of the learners in each region awarded university credits on completion of the course.

Learner awareness regarding the Mooc concept and mission in general, and their perceived value of Moocs for professional development is quite high. In terms of previous experience and awareness of Moocs as a tool for learning, 75% of learners had used Moocs before, and 25% of these had followed 5 or more Moocs. A third of these had predictably followed another language Mooc, but 17% had focused on Computer and data science and 12% on Social Sciences. It is interesting to note that when asked which other Moocs they would be interested in following in the future, many learners

² World Bank Country and Lending Groups. Retrieved from: <https://u.garr.it/nctTU>, last accessed 2025/02/20.

opted for disciplines other than language and 16% selected Political Science as their first choice. Many of the learners identified a direct link between Moocs and SDGs, but a majority said that the language courses aligned with goals of gender equality and climate change, showing that learners were influenced by the topics and cultural context created within the Federica learning design, as much as by the Mooc concept itself.

In terms of how learners reacted to the specific Federica LMoocs and the design features developed for a global audience, the response was positive overall. All 774 respondents except 5 declared that they found the course excellent or good; the animation videos and the avatar tutor videos scored highly in terms of learner appreciation; and a majority said that there was nothing about the course they would change. These responses seem to indicate that the cultural aspects that intentionally informed the design of the learning objects, succeeded in creating a comfortable learning environment for these global learners. In terms of specific learning objects that learners cited as contributing most to their learning, all the diverse activities were considered very, or quite, useful by over 94% of learners, but it was the practical situation tasks with their variety of approach and tools that were rated most highly, closely followed by the numerous interactive practice assignments with feedback, and the specially-reinforced downloadable dictionaries. There is further evidence of convergence on the part of this learning cohort. Although 34% of learners were not aware of the existence of the newly-released Coursera chatbot, the learners who did use it, used it most frequently to generate further practice questions and to ask for more examples of real-life application of the language. Those learners who were unaware of the Coursera AI tutor, tended to use ChatGPT, Claude or Gemini in similar ways. The cohort also made use of other external tools with over half of them using micro-learning apps like Quizlet, Duolingo and AI conversation apps, and 20% using YouTube channels.

6. Final Remarks

The experiences reported can be considered encouraging in relation to the starting point, showing that redesigning courses with a greater focus on cultural aspects and diversifying the content makes the learning experience more comfortable and more effective for a broad global audience in a lifelong learning context. Indeed, the number of active learners on the courses and the number of survey respondents who were willing to engage with a learning community to discuss course improvements and future opportunities seem to suggest that enthusiasm and need for access to quality open language learning content from university providers on a global scale is still high. The respondents demonstrate convergence, but embrace the Moocs as an integral part of their self-learning pathway.

Platform and survey data demonstrate broad geographical uptake, and broad awareness and satisfaction with Moocs as a tool for effective language training in the context of global competency and professional language upskilling, with their coverage of intercultural and communication skills development. The success of the format is con-

firmed by the satisfaction of the users, who appreciated the flexibility of use and diversification of contents provided. In addition, users show a proactive attitude towards possible compensations for the reduced interaction with classmates in the MOOC environment, seeking to be involved in community initiatives and using artificial intelligence tools. Both seem to be interesting areas for development, the first to increase engagement and involvement of learners in order to gather feedback for a better design for a global audience; the second to better understand the autonomous use of tools by learners to support their learning, in order to rethink the design of content and activities based on this awareness. This study, therefore, confirms the importance of continuing the analysis that was started here, and the respondents' willingness to be considered part of a community is the (re)starting point.

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